

PARASITES OF BEES CAUSE EMITS DISEASES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7073285>

Habibullayev Faizulla Nabibullayev ich ,

FarDU support PhD student

Azimova Farangis Khibbatjonovna

Fergana State University

Abstract: *In this article, parasitic diseases of bees in the Fergana Valley and the diseases they cause in bees, their symptoms, methods of prevention and treatment are briefly presented.*

Key words: *bee diseases , varroaosis , invasion , Jacobson mite , wax, larva, queen bee, worker bee, male bee.*

Beekeeping, as one of the branches of agriculture, is kept in order to obtain honey, wax and other products (bee milk, bee glue, bee venom), as well as to pollinate them to increase the productivity of agricultural crops. Attention and interest in beekeeping is increasing year by year . Today, beekeepers are plagued by many bee problems. At the same time, bee stings, bee diseases and parasites that cause them are considered one of the problems. Varroaosis, which is now widespread, is an infectious invasion disease of bees, which is spread by the Jacobson mite. This mite is widespread in many regions of the Fergana Valley and other regions, causing great damage to beekeeping. That's why we tried to clarify the results of observation about some of its features so that every beekeeper should know the development status of this parasitic living mite and measures to combat it. The varroaosis mite is brown in color, visible to the naked eye, and the parasitic mite pierces the body with its mouthparts and has four pairs of legs that attach to the body. Mainly, worker bees, male bees, and in some cases, queen bees (Fargona-April 2022) live with female mites attached to them. Male mites mate with female mites in bee cells (or in male bee hives) and die in worker bee or male bee hives. Ticks found in Fergana Valley: The length of the body of the female tick is on average 1.1 mm, and the width is 1.7 mm; It was observed that the length of the body of the male mite is 1.0 mm and the width is 0.9 mm. The main feeding areas of mites are between the head, thorax and abdomen, and between the 3 anterior abdominal segments. During our transmissions, one worker bee, male bee, or queen bee can have 3 to 5 mites on its body (Markhamat

District, June 2021). According to our research, even in the conditions of the valley, only the female of the varroa mite hibernates (Markhamat district - December 2021) and sexually reproduces in the soft nests of worker bees, queen bees and male bees, developing larvae in their bodies. The female mite enters the incha and lays up to 3 to 8 eggs on the walls of the incha or on the body of the maggots before covering the maggots in the incha. Several female mites can enter the inchas at once to lay eggs. A mite's egg is like an egg, milky white in color. After 8-9 days, the female mite matures from the mite egg laid in the bees' nest, and after 6-7 days, the male mite matures. Female mites mate with male mites in closed bee nests, and ready-to-eat female mites attach to the bees' bodies and come out together when they hatch.

Bed bugs each different 3-5 days without food _ more than live ca n't Our research during the air temperature 30-34°C and 60% humidity of mites the most favorable for reproduction conditions will be considered .. These mites Fergana valley to heat in conditions of 42-44°C and tolerates 0-2°C cold . _ When humidity is 10-12% they are dead will be The sun its rays dislike observed .

Valley conditions female ticks can live hungry for 5-6 days at a temperature of 22-25° C and air humidity of 70-80% (Markhamat District - 2022 April) . In hives without bees, the black caterpillar can live 6-7 days in inches, 15 days in an open worm, 32 days in a closed worm, 3-5 days in the body of dead bees, 7-11 days in the body of a dead hump. Adult female mites feed on the blood of bees (hemolymph), tire the bodies of maggots, humps, and adult bees, develop protein disease, and as a result, the functioning of the bees' body tissues is disturbed, and the bacteria of infectious diseases such as hafniosis, European rot disease, and paratyphoid enter their blood. causes infection and bees begin to die under the influence of two different diseases. As a result of mites sucking the blood from the body of the maggots, when the blood decreases and the thirst for protein increases, the bees drag the maggots to the board in front of the nest hole and take them out. Dead larvae because it smells when used , cells from within easy is taken . The tick is attached bees disturbed by the cells out of the apiary to the bottom spills out . Ticked _ families restless to the village at the entrance one to the ground get together ca n't Theirs growth and honey gathering decreases , this in families mother bee egg to put early in the fall stops . In the fall weakened the rest to the family strong family bees attack does _

Fergana in the valley take went studies based on defining that the infection with varroa mite passes through three different stages can _

1- Mites infect 0.5-2% of bees, and mite infestation does not significantly affect the development of the bee family, if mite control is carried out, the family can be restored.

2- damage, mites damage 3% to 30% of bumblebees , wasps, and male wasps, and it is possible to fight against such damage.

3- bees, humps , and male bees are affected, it is difficult to fight against mites, and in most cases, bee families die .

These are the conclusions amateur to beekeepers the disease prevention take it _ eliminate in reaching hand we think it will come .

The diagnosis of varroa mite is as follows important important have _

- In apiaries, at the end of summer and in autumn, the spreaders of mite diseases are quickly visible and easily identified.

- In the spring and summer months, mites can be found on the bodies of bees, on the larvae and on the mats where the bees land.

- , it is seen that mites are also spilled into the dirty waste at the bottom of the nest possible (Fergana district- 2021 December) .

- Adult wasps and male wasps are more commonly found behind the second and third abdominal joints.

USED LITERATURE .

1. NF Krakhotin . in Uzbekistan beekeeping _ - T.: Labor , 1991.
2. Al Isamuhamedov . Beekeeping . - T.: Teacher , 1995.
3. N. F. Krakhotin. Calendar in pchelovo. - M., 1989.
4. A. G. Avestesian . Beekeeping. - M.
5. A. S. Nujdin . Basic beekeeping. - M., 1988.
6. I. X. Irgashev , S. Starkov. Basic bee diseases and bee diseases. - T.: Mekhnat , 1987.